

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF GUERILLA ADVERTISING CONTENT ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION OF GEN Z

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ABSTRACT

Guerilla Marketing is a new and innovative kind of advertising campaign which creates advertisements which are attractive in nature that are cost saving and strategically creative. It provides information on consumer behaviors in terms of different factors that affect their purchasing intent such as novelty, aesthetics, surprise and humor. Various purposes also include adapting to new media, entering into the dynamic realm of marketing, being on a competitive advantage, and creating a media buzz. The study had used online survey questionnaires through Google Forms as a research instrument in the data collection method. The respondents are from the areas of Valenzuela who are in the population of Gen Z between ages of 16-26. The data analysis compared the relationship between different variables that affects the consumer purchase intention. The analysis covered the mean, standard deviation and regression analysis. The result of linear regression states that novelty, aesthetics, and surprise are not strong indicators of purchase intention. Among the four independent variables, humor has the significant impact on purchase intention. The study concluded that humor has a great impact on the purchasing intent of consumers.

Keywords: *Analysis, Competitive Advantage, Consumer Behavior, Data Analysis, Guerilla Marketing, Mean, Purchasing Intent, Regression, Research Instrument, Standard Deviation*

INTRODUCTION

Guerrilla marketing, also known as guerilla advertising, is a creative and unconventional way to promote a product, service, or brand. Its unconventional and usually low-budget marketing techniques aim to capture the interest of a specific target audience by using novel techniques like humor, surprise, or shock. Street art, public performances, flash mobs, viral videos, and any other unorthodox technique that generates buzz and word-of-mouth media coverage are examples of guerilla advertising. It often requires creative problem solving. Creating a unique and memorable marketing campaign that stands out in the crowded advertising market is the goal. Generally speaking, guerrilla marketing prioritizes the experience and message over large budgets or traditional media channels.

Businesses that want to advertise their products must overcome a number of obstacles. These difficulties can differ based on a number of variables, including the sector, target market, spending limit, and the changing nature of marketing and advertising. Some typical issues are as follows: Selecting the correct audience: Businesses must make sure that the people who are most likely to be interested in their offerings are the ones who see their ads. If you don't, you might end up wasting money on ads. Ad fatigue: Repeated or bothersome advertisements can drive away potential consumers and harm a company's reputation. It can be difficult to strike the correct balance in advertising between variety and frequency. Advertising creativity and quality: It can be very difficult to produce captivating, excellent ads that draw in viewers. Creativity and originality are essential for success. Budgetary restrictions: New and small businesses frequently face difficulties because of their tight advertising budgets, which makes it difficult for them to compete with more established, bigger businesses. It's crucial to identify advertising tactics that are affordable. Changes to the ad platform: Platforms, algorithms, and laws are all part of the ever-changing landscape of advertising. Businesses need to adjust to these developments and keep abreast of emerging technologies and trends in advertising. Competition: It is more difficult to outperform rivals in advertising efforts when so many businesses are fighting for the attention of the same target audience.

Guerrilla marketing content aimed at Generation Z (Gen Z) should create memorable, unique, and captivating experiences that speak to the preferences and behaviors of this demographic in order to influence purchase intention. Novelty is a marketing strategy that has the potential to positively impact purchase intention. A brand or product can have a distinctive and alluring value proposition when customers believe it to be innovative and powerful. Aesthetics: this refers to using design, creativity, and aesthetic appeal to increase a campaign's efficacy. In order to grab people's attention, make an impression, and deliver the desired message, aesthetics are vital. Surprise is the art of using unusual and unexpected components to craft unforgettable experiences. In guerilla marketing, surprise has the power to grab attention, create buzz, and make a lasting impression on the target audience. Using humorous elements strategically to create memorable and captivating experiences is what humor is all about. Funny things

can draw people in, elicit good feelings, and make them more likely to tell others about them.

In the current economic climate, people are exposed to a broader variety of commercial messages that cannot be understood unless they immediately catch the attention of the audience. Customers are becoming more adept at avoiding being swayed by traditional advertising, whether through the use of new technologies or by merely cognitively ignoring it. In order to retain their clients, advertisers had to use creative, original, and out-of-the-box tactics, methods, and approaches. They had used several new advertising media that didn't meet audience expectations. Guerrilla marketing tactics use unorthodox approaches to communicate innovative ideas in a dynamic manner in unexpected locations. The consumer is intended to be surprised, irritated, fascinated, and animated. Guerrilla marketing tactics are defined as being more innovative and striking than conventional methods. When consumers perceive the benefits of guerilla marketing, they are more likely to support and identify the company's brand, which can improve consumer brand awareness and high buy intent.

According to (Zarco & Herzallah, 2023) a lot of companies have started acting more creatively in an attempt to lead the market because of the intense competition for new products and services in recent years. "Guerrilla marketing" refers to a type of advertising that uses creative thinking and a range of low-cost strategies. Since this concept was first introduced in the latter half of the 20th century, a great deal of research has been done to investigate its application and efficacy. This study provides a systematic assessment of the marketing and advertising field by using content analysis to examine the major scientific articles on guerrilla marketing in the Web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCO databases.

Today's businesses are mainly focused on attracting clients, holding their interest, and ultimately retaining them for an extended amount of time. One such tactic is guerrilla marketing, which draws clients by employing odd or distinctive methods. These strategies rely more on the imagination and inventiveness of the person organizing and carrying out the campaign than they do on financial resources (Ravindran, 2019).

Remember that aesthetics had the largest impact on purchase intention when participating in guerilla marketing-related activities. To engage target audiences, businesses and advertising agencies must also devise novel (creative) communication strategies. Surprise and humor—the two main ways that guerilla marketing differs from traditional marketing—had a significant effect on purchase intention. In the context of guerilla marketing, positive reinforcers like novelty, aesthetics, surprise, and humor should be prioritized.

Mehmood and Masood (2016) contend that humorous advertising has a major impact on consumers' intentions to make purchases. Humor in advertising increases the desire to buy, but if it is done badly or in an inappropriate way, it can damage the source company's reputation (Christensen & Skoggard, 2017). The comic effect can lower barriers between consumers and brands and greatly increase the number of receivers.

Customers are becoming more interested in novel, unconventional advertising strategies, so marketers are trying to grab their attention with visually striking messages. Guerrilla marketing is one special method for meeting this requirement. Guerrilla marketing is a popular marketing strategy that promotes products and services through unusual means. The purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between purchase intention and specific demographic variables, as well as the impact of guerilla marketing .In Egypt, a sample of 400 respondents was surveyed using a quantitative approach. The findings indicated that consumer purchase intention is positively impacted by advertisements' inventiveness, emotional arousal, clarity, humor, and surprise. It was discovered that women had a greater influence on purchase intention than did men. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that age has no discernible impact on consumers' intentions to make purchases..

A product's level of craftsmanship and visual appeal are good measures of how novel people think it is. This is not beauty per se; rather, aesthetics refers to harmony and the methodical construction of the message. It is the arrangement of signs to create intricate relationships. When something has a specific effect on cognitive reference, such as the evaluation of guerilla marketing, it is imperative to discuss the aesthetics component. What advertising can accomplish artistic effects "by purposefully breaching specific coding conventions, to initiate overlapping and entwining semantic chains that are not typically connected."

In accordance to Ahmad (2023) Social media marketing, a vital part of business management, is the success factor in attaining purchase intention. This study sheds new light on how social media marketing campaigns influence the purchase intentions of younger consumers. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how Malaysian Generation Z's buying intentions are affected by social media marketing. 339 respondents were analyzed both descriptively and inferentially using a straightforward sampling technique in this study. To gather information on social media activity, quantitative surveys based on model constructs were created. Correlation analysis was used to perform the analysis on the data with the use of SPSS statistical analysis software. The purchasing intention of customers has been greatly influenced by all social media marketing activity variables. Trendiness is the best indication, followed by perceived trust and brand recognition, in that order. Organizations will learn from the research how important social media is to influencing audience perceptions that in turn influence consumer purchase intention.

While traditional advertising requires specific financial resources for its promotion, guerilla marketing primarily requires the investment of time, energy, creativity, and knowledge, according to Tam, D. D., and Khương, M. N. (2015). Guerrilla marketing requires a company to be able to stand out from its competitors and effectively reach those potential customers. For guerrilla tactics to be effective and accomplish this, they need to be unique. According to the study, novelty is the special qualities of a product that set it apart from the competition and that the buyer felt had a very strong positive connotation.

In accordance to (Clemente Eke, 2022) This research looks at how guerrilla marketing affects Calabar consumers' use of noodles. This study's primary goal was to investigate the connection between consumer patronage and guerilla marketing. The primary research design was chosen to be the survey design. There were 200 questionnaires given as part of the study's total sample size. The structured questionnaire served as the data gathering tool. The degree of association was measured using a straightforward linear regression analysis. According to the study, ambient and viral marketing significantly increased consumer spending. Based on the findings, consumer patronage rises when guerrilla marketing strategies are implemented. Additionally, there is a good chance that customer patronage will rise if the guerilla marketing proxies that are currently available—viral and ambient marketing—are given more prominence. The researchers suggested that distributors concentrate on using innovative and creative advertising, and that they should engage in viral marketing as they generate positive online word-of-mouth for the company's products.

According to Palikhe (2018) Analyzing the "Impact of Humor advertisement on Purchase Intention of Consumer Perception" is the primary goal of this essay. In order to accomplish the goal, a descriptive research approach is employed to gather the required market data through the use of questionnaires. With the aid of computer software, primary and secondary data were employed for analysis. The influence of humorous advertisements on consumers' perceptions of what to buy is analyzed using factors such as age, gender, education, and religion. Consequently, many tables are created and analyzed that include the percentage, mean, and standard deviation. A correlation research has been conducted between purchase intention and humorous commercials. At the 0.01 level of significance, the correlation is significant since the P value is smaller than alpha, or $0.00 < 0.01$. Every hypothesis that was tested was found to be significant at the 1% significance level. It was discovered to have a positive correlation. It was discovered that purchase intention was favorably and strongly correlated with humorous advertisements.

The people who were born between 1997 and 2012 are referred to as the current Generation Gen-Z, also known as the I-Generation or Centennials, according to Sharma, D., & Srivastav, P. (2023). They are the progeny of the previous generation, the Millennials. Numerous studies and examinations have revealed that a specific group of individuals tends to act differently from other groups in terms of their interests and preferences. Because of the various circumstances that each generation faces as a result of changes in social structures, economic systems, and technology, they all develop unique values and tend to view the world from their own viewpoint.

According to (Calleja, I. J. G. 2019) Social networking sites have emerged as a means for business owners to reach a larger audience with their marketing initiatives in today's technologically advanced world. This is particularly valid for businesses looking to acquire a competitive edge. Businesses need to understand how to use social media in a way that aligns with their business plan because of this trend. In light of this, the study set out to ascertain whether social media is a useful instrument for some businesses' marketing campaigns. In particular, the study aimed to address the following questions:

how much time respondents spent on social media, how often they used it, how often they saw company ads using social media, and how effective social media marketing was in terms of attention, interest, desire, and action; how much difference there was in the effectiveness of social media marketing when respondents were categorized based on their age and gender; and how much time respondents spent on social media and how often they saw company ads using social media.

(Bekir Özkan, 2022) In addition to small enterprises, large corporations have been utilizing guerilla marketing tactics since they are more creative and can be implemented on a shoestring budget. The goal of this study is to investigate how customer attitudes and perceptions of guerrilla marketing practices affect consumers' intentions to make purchases. In this vein, research is being done on how guerrilla marketing advertisements affect consumers' intentions to buy based on elements including originality, clarity, comedy, emotional arousal, and surprise. To this end, the SPSS software is used to analyze data from 361 individuals. The collected data indicates that purchase intention is positively and significantly impacted by creativity, comedy, emotional arousal, and surprise, but not by clarity.

Advertisements serve to elicit specific emotions, which in turn affect consumers' intentions to make purchases. Ads commonly employ humor as a powerful means of expressing information in order to evoke strong feelings in the viewer. The study suggests that humor stimulation in advertisements can affect consumers' new product purchase intentions, in which two process mechanisms, namely, emotional arousal and cognitive flexibility, play a mediating role. It draws on literature on advertisement humor and new product purchase intention as well as the theory of planned behavior. Results of this study indicate that consumers who watch humorous advertisements are more likely to choose new products than those who watch non-humorous advertisements (Study 1); in addition, humorous advertisements have the potential to increase emotional arousal in comparison to non-humorous advertisements, which can foster cognitive flexibility and increase the likelihood that consumers will choose new products (Studies 2 and 3). Nevertheless, the writers discover that these mediation effects are only partially present. Originality/value: The findings of this study have significant ramifications for businesses hoping to increase consumers' inclinations to acquire new products by using hilarious advertisements. (Du, Shen, Durmusoglu, and Li, 2023)

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to ascertain how consumer purchase intent is impacted by guerilla advertising content.

In significance, it sought to answer the following queries:

Research Question no. 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1 Age
- 1.2 Gender
- 1.3 Location

Research Question no.2: What is the impact of the guerrilla advertising content to purchase intention of RC Cola in terms of :

- 2.1 Novelty
 - 2.2 Aesthetics
 - 2.3 Surprise
 - 2.4 Humor
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METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is to address every aspect of research methodology, including research design, research location, population and sampling, research ethics, research instruments, data collection, and data analysis, which is used to carry out this study.

Research Design

Many components of experimental design can be included into quasi-experimental designs, which are simpler to implement in some study types. The quasi-experimental design is commonly used in the social sciences. More specifically, quasi-experimental research is often used in criminology, criminal justice, and assessment studies. The output of effect estimates from various quasi-experimental designs varies, but in general, interrupted time series and regression discontinuity are regarded as robust quasi-experimental methods. The one-group pre-test and post-test design, the post-test-only with nonequivalent groups design, and the one-group post-test-only design, however, are the weakest. The researchers used quasi experimental design, an approach to study when participants are not randomly assigned to experimental and control groups is known as a quasi-experimental design. Although it is similar to real trials, it is less rigorous in controlling factors because it usually incorporates pre-existing groups. In situations where random assignment is difficult or immoral, researchers employ quasi-experimental designs.

Research Locale

The study focused on the Gen Z demographic, found an ideal setting in Valenzuela because of its large and diverse population. Because the city has a high proportion of residents in the target age group, the researchers chose it on purpose to ensure a deeper comprehension of the topic. Furthermore, Valenzuela was selected because it was a dependable and convenient location for the research, which made data collection and analysis easier.

Population and Sampling

Researchers selected Gen Z, defined as those between the ages of 16 and 26, as study participants because, as technology continues to advance, Gen Z is beginning to interact and participate more become acquainted on social media. Through expert

evaluation, the researchers were able to select sampling units solely based on their expertise and select samples relevant to their area of expertise. By employing a non-probability selection method known as "purposeful sampling," researchers select study participants based on pre-established criteria relevant to the investigation's objective. Unlike random sampling, purposeful sampling involves a targeted and deliberate selection process to gather data from individuals who meet predetermined criteria. The research has a sample size of one hundred respondents and the sample size is calculated by G- Power. G *Power can also be used to compute effect sizes and graphically display the results of power analyses.

Research Ethics

The Data Privacy Act of 2012 (DPA), also referred to as Republic Act No. 10173, is an official government law that aims to protect personal data in communications and information systems utilized by the public and private sectors. In order to fulfill the obligations regarding the confidentiality of their respondents, researchers adhere to research ethics. To prevent a bad reaction between the researcher and respondents, the respondents have given their formal consent. To prevent any misunderstandings, the researcher needs to obtain both the respondent's signature and a printed consent. The consent form needs to outline the steps and tell the interviewees everything they need to know. The consent outlines the guidelines, protocols, and advantages of the research.

Research Instruments

Online Questionnaires

The internet was the main resource utilized by the researchers to gather survey data. The Gen Z residents of Valenzuela City completed the survey by filling out a Google form, which is a popular online survey tool. The first section of the questionnaire consists of the respondent's demographic information, which includes name, address, gender, and age. The five sets of questions pertaining to the five variables come next. Because Google Forms has so many advantages, it's a reliable option for conducting surveys. First of all, it makes data collection convenient and accessible for participants by enabling researchers to gather it from any location. Second, researchers can save time and effort by using the automated data analysis feature of Google Forms. In order to protect participant data security and confidentiality, it also provides features like password-protected access and distinct study IDs. Additionally, it has been discovered that employing Google Forms for online surveys enhances data when compared to paper-based surveys. Not to add, Google Forms is an affordable choice because it does away with the need for paper-based responses and manual data entry, which lowers the costs related to collecting and analyzing data. The online survey's results are available for analysis at any moment. See results instantly so you can take appropriate action, make graphs for reporting, export data for additional analysis, and communicate your findings with anyone.

Likert Scale

The researchers also used Likert scale, a psychometric measurement tool that is used in surveys and questionnaires to assess people's attitudes, perceptions, opinions, or behaviors regarding a specific topic or statement. It bears the name of its creator, Rensis Likert. It's one of the rating scales that researchers use the most, particularly in the social sciences and market research. Respondents mark their degree of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements or items that make up the scale. It typically falls between strongly disagreeing and strongly agreeing, though there may be some variances depending on the situation.

Data Collection

People of any gender between the ages of 16 and 26 who have watched the advertisement will participate in this study to evaluate the impact of guerilla advertising on Gen Z's purchase intentions. The research questionnaire was distributed digitally via Google Forms, which allowed for the collection of the data for the study. The research questionnaire was released to the public by the researchers following its validation; it was shared via email and posts on social media sites like Facebook and Messenger. There were sections for informed consent and instructions on the Google Forms. After respondents finished filling out the survey, each response was noted. The results were automatically calculated using Google Forms. Each response was then totaled, scrutinized, and analyzed by the researchers. During the survey, participants were at liberty to pose any queries or communicate any apprehensions they might have had to the researchers. The researcher used a Google form to gather data. One hundred respondents make up the sample size for this study, which is determined using G-Power. Effect sizes can also be calculated and power analysis results can be visually represented using G *Power

Data Analysis

Mean

The mean, also referred to as the average, is a measure of central tendency in statistics. The computation involves summing up all the values present in a data set and dividing the result by the total number of values. Because it is influenced by all of the dataset's values and is comparatively simple to understand, the mean is frequently used. Extreme values, or outliers, have the potential to distort the average. Other central tendency measurements, such as the median or mode, may be more appropriate in certain situations.

Standard Deviation

A measure of how much variation or dispersion there is in a set of values is the standard deviation. It indicates the degree to which a dataset's values diverge from the mean (average). When the standard deviation is low, it means that the data points are generally near to the mean; when it is high, it means that the data points are dispersed

over a larger range. To find the formula, take the square root of the average of the squared deviations between the mean and each data point. In many disciplines, such as science, statistics, and finance, the standard deviation is helpful because it makes it possible to evaluate the validity of the mean as a representative number and comprehend how data is distributed.

Regression Analysis

A statistical method for determining the relationship between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable is regression analysis. It is frequently used in many disciplines, such as the social sciences, natural sciences, and economics. Without more information, I am unable to cite a specific source, but I can suggest a general reference that discusses regression analysis. (J. Cohen, P. Cohen, West, and Aiken, 2003)

RESULTS

4.1 Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic			Frequency	Percentage
Age	Location	Gender		
16-26	Valenzuela	Male & Female	109	100%

There are 109 respondents in Valenzuela area in this study. The selected individuals are from Generation Z (16–26 years old) which finished this research study's 100% sample.

4.2 Table 2: Descriptive

Variables	Mean	SD
Novelty	3.42	.41
Aesthetics	3.45	.45

Surprise	3.42	.45
Humor	3.41	.48
Purchase Intention	3.27	.57
TOTAL	3.39	0.07

4.3 Table 3: Linear Regression

3.1. Novelty

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Novelty And Purchase Intention	0.549	0.820	-0.034	Accept Ho1: Novelty is not a significant predictor of Purchase Intention

Significance is accepted at $<.05$ P-Value

The impact of Novelty on the purchase intention is displayed in the table above. The results indicate the analysis of the data using linear regression, providing the researchers with a 0.820 as the p-value. Considering the decision rule that directs investigators to accept the null. The null hypothesis was accepted based on the obtained result if the significant difference was greater than 0.05. Consequently, novelty is not a strong indicator of purchase intention. Additionally, the two variables have a positive

moderately strong correlation (0.549) between the two factors, and the likelihood of making a purchase decreases by -0.034 for every unit of novelty.

Table 3.2: Aesthetics

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Aesthetics And Purchase Intention	0.614	0.548	0.088	Accept Ho2: Aesthetics is not a significant predictor of Purchase Intention

Significance is accepted at <.05 P-Value

The impact of Aesthetics on the purchase intention is displayed in the table above. The results indicate the analysis of the data using linear regression, providing the researchers with a 0.548 as the p-value. Considering the decision rule that directs investigators to accept the null. The null hypothesis was accepted based on the obtained result if the significant difference was greater than 0.05. Consequently, aesthetics is not a strong indicator of purchase intention. Additionally, the two variables have a positive high strong correlation (0.614) between the two factors, and the likelihood of making a purchase increases by 0.088 for every unit of aesthetics.

Table 3.3: Surprise

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Surprise And Purchase Intention	0.676	0.148	0.222	Accept Ho3: Surprise is not a significant predictor of Purchase Intention

Significance is accepted at $<.05$ P-Value

The impact of Surprise on the purchase intention is displayed in the table above. The results indicate the analysis of the data using linear regression, providing the researchers with a 0.148 as the p-value. Considering the decision rule that directs investigators to accept the null. The null hypothesis was accepted based on the obtained result if the significant difference was greater than 0.05. Consequently, surprise is not a strong indicator of purchase intention. Additionally, the two variables have a positive high strong correlation (0.676) between the two factors, and the likelihood of making a purchase increases by 0.222 for every unit of surprise.

Table 3.4: Humor

Variable	Pearson correlation	P-Value	Regression Coefficient	Decision Rule and Interpretation
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Humor	0.759	<0.001	0.685	Reject Ho4:
And Purchase				Humor is a
Intention				significant predictor
				of Purchase Intention

Significance is accepted at <.05 P-Value

The impact of Humor on the purchase intention is displayed in the table above. The results indicate the analysis of the data using linear regression, providing the researchers with a <0.001 as the p-value. Considering the decision rule that directs investigators to reject the null. The null hypothesis was rejected based on the obtained result if the significant difference was greater than 0.05. Consequently, humor is a strong indicator of purchase intention. Additionally, the two variables have a positive high strong correlation (0.759) between the two factors, and the likelihood of making a purchase increases by 0.685 for every unit of humor.

DISCUSSION

The research output-based summary of the current study's findings and implications. The limitations, findings, and possible future directions of this study are all thoroughly discussed. With a total of 0.07, the results for novelty, aesthetics, surprise, humor, and buy intention were (0.41), (0.45), (0.48), and (0.57), according to the standard deviation. Among the four independent variables, humor significantly influences the intention to buy.

The study looked at the impact of a number of factors, such as novelty, aesthetics, surprise, and humor, on the intention to buy, according to the results summary. The standard deviations provide a measure of the variability in responses for each component. Although the low standard deviations suggest generally consistent results, the linear regression analysis in this instance reveals that novelty, aesthetics, and surprise are not significant predictors of purchase intention. However, humor is a significant factor that influences purchase intention. The study offers valuable insights to industry professionals by highlighting the distinct influence of humor on purchase intention in its conclusion. Researchers should consider expanding their scope of analysis or streamlining their methodology in order to gain a deeper understanding of consumer behavior.

Conclusions

This study looks at how Gen Z in Metro Manila is affected by novelty, aesthetics, surprise, and humor when they see guerilla advertising content on various social media platforms. Customers might leave a lasting impression thanks to the wealth of technology available today and the rising number of people with Internet access. This impression could be shared worldwide. Campaigns for marketing have the power to go viral fast and touch a vast number of people. The results of the study indicate that Gen Z's purchase intention was influenced by guerilla advertising content. Additionally, the four study variables are the most important ones.

It is also discovered that the study's variables significantly predict consumers' intentions to make purchases. It shows that the respondent's intention to buy increased with each unit of independent variables that used guerilla advertising content. This proves that each variable used had a major role in the guerilla marketing collateral. Based on the study's findings, the researchers concluded that humor has a greater influence on consumers' purchase intentions ($p < 0.001$). Surprise received the lowest results, with a 0.148 coefficient, indicating that surprise has the least influence on consumers' intentions to make purchases.

Recommendations

The researchers provided the following recommendations based on the findings and conclusions.

Based on the study's findings, the researchers concluded that humor has significant influence on consumers' purchase intentions ($p < 0.001$). By stressing the use of humor to grab and hold Gen Z consumers' attention, this recommendation report seeks to assist guerilla marketing advertisement in improving its marketing approach.

Using the four variables, the researchers created this study to investigate the effect of guerilla advertising content on Gen Z consumers' purchase intentions. The researcher recommends and encourages businesses to try guerilla marketing as a means of promoting their goods and services because the results of the study demonstrate that this type of marketing is successful in spreading viral advertising content. Running sponsored ad campaigns on social media platforms to target particular consumers is known as social media advertising. Through social media sites like LinkedIn, Pinterest, Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter, advertisers and marketers can persuade customers to purchase their goods and services. The study also found that humor is a significant predictor of purchase intention among the four variables. Martin (2006) claims that understanding the psychological point of view is simple. In essence, humor is a happy feeling known as "mirth," which is demonstrated by laughing in facial and vocal expressions. In social situations, humor is usually evoked by a cognitive appraisal process that involves the perception of lighthearted, non-serious incognitive expressions. Companies should be motivated to work with influencers on various social media networks. Companies can improve their brand positioning, image, and value by choosing

the right influencers. The researcher strongly advises incorporating humor as much as possible into their advertising material since it increases consumers' propensity to make purchases. They should also incorporate surprise elements into their guerilla advertising material. People are drawn to surprising content, and this increases the chance that it will be shared. Think of unique approaches, unexpected turns, or novel insights to make the content stand out. The element of surprise can aid in the virality of their campaign by drawing in Gen Z consumers, who are known for seeking out unique and creative experiences. Finally, exercise caution when using comedy, making sure that it adheres to moral standards and stays away from sensitive or potentially offensive subjects. Since humor is subjective, what one group of people finds funny may offend another. To comprehend the quirks and sensitivity of your target audience—especially the Gen Z cohort—conduct in-depth market research. Establishing and maintaining a positive brand image depends heavily on ethical considerations. Aim for diversity and get rid of stereotypes that might alienate particular audience segments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Compliance with ethical standards is a crucial element in ensuring the integrity, validity, and societal approval of research endeavors. To uphold such standards, several key principles and practices are essential. The first pertains to Informed Consent, emphasizing that participants should be fully briefed on the research's nature, purpose, and potential risks. Consent must be freely given, devoid of coercion, and participants retain the right to withdraw at their discretion. Another fundamental aspect involves Confidentiality and Privacy, obligating researchers to safeguard participants' privacy and maintain the confidentiality of their data. This encompasses secure data storage and meticulous handling of sensitive information. Additionally, ethical research is characterized by the principle of Beneficence, whereby the research aims for positive outcomes, such as advancing knowledge or improving practices, with benefits outweighing potential risks. The principle of Respect for Persons underscores the acknowledgment of the autonomy and dignity of all participants, including vulnerable groups. Furthermore, ethical research extends to Data Management and Sharing, necessitating transparent and responsible handling of data during and after the research is concluded.

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QUESTIONS	4	3	2	1
1. The Guerilla Marketing YouTube advertisement presented a novel and unique approach.				
2. I found the content of the Guerilla Marketing YouTube advertisement to be innovative.				
3. The advertisement offered something different from other typical marketing approaches.				
4. The use of unconventional methods in the advertisement caught my attention.				
5. The advertisement presented a fresh and new perspective.				
6. The visual elements of the Guerilla Marketing YouTube advertisement were visually appealing.				
7. The overall design of the advertisement was aesthetically pleasing.				
8. The use of colors and graphics in the advertisement was appealing.				
9. The advertisement had a professional and polished appearance.				
10. The visual aspects of the advertisement enhanced my overall impression.				
11. I was surprised with the content or approach used in the advertisement.				
12. The element of surprise in the advertisement captured my attention				
13. The unexpected aspects of the advertisement were engaging.				
14. The surprise elements in the advertisement made it memorable.				

15. The Guerilla Marketing YouTube advertisement surprised me in a positive way.				
16. The humor used in the Guerilla Marketing YouTube advertisement was enjoyable.				
17. The comedic elements enhanced my overall experience with the advertisement.				
18. The use of humor in the advertisement was appropriate for the product.				
19. The humor in the advertisement positively influenced my perception of the brand.				
20. The advertisement effectively used humor to convey its message.				
21. I am more likely to purchase the RC products after seeing the advertisement.				
22. The advertisement made me want to learn more about the RC products.				
23. The advertisement made me consider purchasing the product.				
24. The advertisement left a positive impression on me.				
25. Overall, the advertisement increased my likelihood of making a purchase of RC Products.				